

Khalka Mongols

also known as “Monggol (in Mongolian)”, “Mongolia”, “Mongolians”, “Mongols”, “Menggu (in Chinese)”

Data source: eHRAF

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Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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Entry tags: Religion, Buddhist Traditions, Mongolian Buddhism, Mongolian Religions, Mongolian Shamanism

The Mongol cultural group contains several sub-groups (the Khalka, Buriat, and Oirats). While these sub-groups exhibit commonalities, they are unique communities with nuanced distinctions and are located in different geographic regions. This entry focuses specifically on the Khalkha Mongols of the Narobanchin Temple Territory, in western Outer Mongolia (ca. 1920) before the influx of Communism and Japanese occupation.

Date Range: 1895 CE - 1930 CE

Region: Mongolia ca. 1920

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, Mongolia

This entry focuses specifically on the Khalkha Mongols of the Narobanchin Temple Territory, in what was historically western Outer Mongolia (now Mongolia). (ca. 1920)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/ehrafe/>

– Source 1 Description: eHRAF World Cultures: Khalka Mongols (Mongolia: AH01)

– Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ah01-016>

– Source 2 Description: Vreeland, H.H. 1954. *Mongol Community and Kinship Structure*. New Haven. (D.G. Hutukhtu, informant, 1950-1952; reconstruction of the 1920 period.)

– Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ah01-014>

–Source 3 Description: Maiskii, I. M. (Ivan Mikhailovich), Mrs. Dayton, and J. Kunitz. 1921. "Contemporary Mongolia." Irkutsk: Gosudarstvennoe Izdatel'stvo, Irkutskoe Otdelenie.

Notes: Vreeland, 1954: (D.G. Hutukhtu, informant, 1950-1952; reconstruction of the 1920 period.) Maiskii, I. 1921: Contains general information on Mongolian culture and is not specific to the focal community. This source should be used cautiously.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Khalka Mongols have had contact with Tibetan Buddhists since the sixteenth century (eHRAF World Cultures: Culture Summary of the Khalka Mongols)

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The Mongols frequently traded with the Chinese (Vreeland, 1973:29).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating) code=9, "internal warfare seems to occur once every 2 years (original code 3)". SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification code=2, "inferred to be unpacified because warfare frequency is greater than or equal to 3". (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), "external warfare seems to occur at least once every two years" (code=10, original code=3.25). SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification (code=2), "inferred to be unpacified because warfare frequency is greater than or equal to 3". (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1800

Notes: "The total population of the territory was between 1600 and 2000 persons. About 300 of these were priests, or lamas, and most of this [Page 10] number were normally resident at the temple. The rest of the population was distributed in the herding camps, in family units. The informant is unable to estimate the number of camps in the territory, but states that there were about 400

independent family units, or households, distributed in the camps. The camps appear to have consisted of about 1-3 households, and using this as a rough gauge, we may set the number of camps tentatively at about 200" (Vreeland, 1954:9).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In this society, the Lama Church leads both religious and civil realms (Vreeland, 1954). "The organization of the temple begins with the two Living Buddhas who presided over both the civil and religious departments of the administration of the temple and its territory. Both Living Buddhas were lamas with the special status of "incarnation," or hubilgaan, and with the rank of hutaktuu" (Vreeland, 1954:93).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: See Vreeland, 1954, Chapter II, section on Religious Organization

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: "The organization of the temple begins with the two Living Buddhas who presided over both the civil and religious departments of the administration of the temple and its territory" (Vreeland, 1954:93).

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 10

Notes: Dilowa Hutukhtu Narobanchin Hutukhtu Kamba Corji Santsab Da lama Cohacin gesgüi (big) Cohacin gesgüi (small) Cohacin loban Demci See Vreeland, 1954, Chapter II, section on Religious Organization

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "The organization of the temple begins with the two Living Buddhas who presided over both the civil and religious departments of the administration of the temple and its territory. Both Living Buddhas were lamas with the special status of "incarnation," or hubilgaan, and with the rank of hutaktuu. The status of hubilgaan was acquired by a layman upon his selection as the successor, or reincarnation, of a deceased hubilgaan, a particular succession of hubilgaan going back ultimately to one of the Hindu bodhisattvas. The qualifications for a successor were that he be born shortly after the death of the previous hubilgaan, and that he be marked by some unusual signs or circumstances attending his birth. Extended searches for infants meeting these qualifications were commenced as soon as possible after a hubilgaan died. During the Manchu regime this involved ascertaining, by divination, of a general direction for the search; the preparation by local monasteries in the designated search area of lists of possible candidates known to them; and the selection from these lists of the most likely successor" (Vreeland, 1954:94).

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in the sense that powers are acquired by reincarnation (see quote above) (Vreeland, 1954:94).

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: A committee of five leaders will select candidates, and the Living Buddhas will select leaders for this committee. See Vreeland, 1954, Chapter II, section on Religious Organization

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: A committee of five leaders will select candidates, and the Living Buddhas will select leaders for this committee. See Vreeland, 1954, Chapter II, section on Religious Organization

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: "In addition to their routine duties, the da lama, demci, the two cohacin gesgüi, and the agba gesgüi served on a committee of five which was convened for certain periodic administrative matters. In this committee all had equal voice in the discussions, but the da lama and the two cohacin gesgüi stood highest in authority and had each separate veto power. If these last officials were unable to reach agreement on some point, the matter was referred to the kamba; if the kamba could not decide, it went to the santsab; and if the santsab could not decide it went to the Living Buddhas. The two Living Buddhas then decided the matter jointly, and it is reported that there was never any conflict between them" (Vreeland, 1954:96).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "In Buddhist belief the corpse of a man may not be buried in the earth but must be given to the beasts and the birds to be eaten by them. If after this the corpse is eaten, then the family of the deceased consider that their duty has been fulfilled and that the soul of the deceased has been cleansed and taken into eternal bliss" (Maiskii, 1921:136).

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: See Vreeland, 1954, Chapter II: Khalkha Mongols of the Narobanchin Territory

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: See Vreeland, 1954, Chapter II: Khalkha Mongols of the Narobanchin Territory

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: "As is known, Buddhists believe in the transmigration of the soul. Accordingly, the Mongol when he is dying does not doubt that his soul after having taken leave of its present body shall come back to earth, reincarnated in the body of some other living creature. The only thing the Mongol worries about is that his soul find a more or less decent dwelling place, that it enter the body of a human being, or at least of some noble animal, such as a horse or a dog, and not into something like a despicable snake or an impure insect. And since a "good rebirth" is granted to him whose life was well-lived and virtuous, the Mongol who does not feel that he has committed any special sins is quite at peace when he faces the inevitable end" (Maiskii, 1921:135).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "In Buddhist belief the corpse of a man may not be buried in the earth but must be given to the beasts and the birds to be eaten by them. Accordingly, the Mongols do not bury their dead in graves, but throw them into the fields where the carnivora and the weather very soon accomplish their destructive task. When death finally comes, the body, dressed in poor clothes, is taken out of the yurt, not through the doorway, but through an opening in the wall, especially made for this purpose. Accompanied by the lama, the body is carried to the previously designated spot. There the corpse is laid on the ground, a small pillow is put under its head, and a Tibetan prayerbook is placed in its hands. Thus prepared (p.56) the body is covered with a [Page 137] piece of rough material, which is fastened down by four stones placed on the corners. This completes the burial. The people withdraw, and the beasts and nature take their toll. If the corpse remains untouched for several days – it is a sign that the gods are angry. Then the disconcerted relatives invite a lama to visit the corpse, the lama conducts services over it and entreats the higher powers to forgive the sinner and to send him an easy end – i.e., to direct the attention of beasts and birds to his mortal remains. If after this the corpse is eaten, then the family of the deceased consider that their duty has been fulfilled and that the soul of the deceased has been cleansed and taken into eternal bliss" (Maiskii, 1921:136).

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Yes

Notes: "In Buddhist belief the corpse of a man may not be buried in the earth but must be given to the beasts and the birds to be eaten by them. Accordingly, the Mongols do not bury their dead in graves, but throw them into the fields where the carnivora and the weather very soon accomplish their destructive task" (Maiskii, 1921:136).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Formal burials are present in the Khalka society, but the body is not actually buried beneath the earth. A cloth is laid over the body and it is placed on the ground to be consumed by the elements and natural world (Maiskii, 1921:136). See previous question for detailed ethnographic information.

Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Sky Burial

Notes: "In Buddhist belief the corpse of a man may not be buried in the earth but must be given to the beasts and the birds to be eaten by them. Accordingly, the Mongols do not bury their dead in graves, but throw them into the fields where the carnivora and the weather very soon accomplish their destructive task. When death finally comes, the body, dressed in poor clothes, is taken out of the yurt, not through the doorway, but through an opening in the wall, especially made for this purpose. Accompanied by the lama, the body is carried to the previously designated spot. There the corpse is laid on the ground, a small pillow is put under its head, and a Tibetan prayerbook is placed in its hands. Thus prepared (p.56) the body is covered with a [Page 137] piece of rough material, which is fastened down by four stones placed on the corners. This completes the burial. The people withdraw, and the beasts and nature take their toll. If the corpse remains untouched for several days – it is a sign that the gods are angry. Then the disconcerted relatives invite a lama to visit the corpse, the lama conducts services over it and entreats the higher powers to forgive the sinner and to send him an easy end – i.e., to direct the attention of beasts and birds to his mortal remains. If after this the corpse is eaten, then the family of the deceased consider that their duty has been fulfilled and that the soul of the deceased has been cleansed and taken into eternal bliss" (Maiskii, 1921:136).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are believed to cause illness, so supernatural beings must be present. SCCS Variable 654, Theories of Spirit Aggression, code=4, "Predominant cause recognized by the society". Theories of Spirit Aggression is defined as "the attribution of illness to the direct hostile, arbitrary, or punitive action of some malevolent or affronted supernatural being". (Murdock and Wilson, 1978; retrieved from Divale, 2004). The most reliable ethnographic information on the Narobanchin Temple territory mentions the presence of spirits and supernatural beings, but does not provide enough detail on the nature of these beings to conclusively answer many of the following questions.

A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: A supreme high god is most likely not present. No evidence has been found in the ethnographic data to indicate the presence of a supreme high god, however, this does not mean a definitive absence.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: "Laymen expressed their integration into the community from a religious standpoint primarily by supporting the church with contributions of personnel, goods and services. Every family tried to send at least one son to the church to become a lama; lama sons and their teachers, or baksi, were supported by the lay families; goods and services were contributed to the temple treasuries, or to temple-managed activities – e.g. general services at the temple, general oboo festivals, the yearly game festival; and contributions were made to the two Living Buddhas" (Vreeland, 1954:111).

Other:

– Yes [specify]: To the temple

Notes: "Laymen expressed their integration into the community from a religious standpoint primarily by supporting the church with contributions of personnel, goods and services. Every family tried to send at least one son to the church to become a lama; lama sons and their teachers, or baksi, were supported by the lay families; goods and services were contributed to the temple treasuries, or to temple-managed activities – e.g. general services at the temple, general oboo festivals, the yearly game festival; and contributions were made to the two Living Buddhas" (Vreeland, 1954:111).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Khalka Mongols ultimately fall under the rule of the Chinese Empire. "Prior to the revolution of 1912, Outer Mongolia was part of the Chinese Empire of the Ch'ing dynasty, and was controlled by indirect rule from Peking. By 1912, it has been divided for administrative purposes into several major territorial compartments. Each of these compartments was called an aimak, and the eastern four were known as the Khalkha aimak. Each of the Khalkha aimak was subdivided into smaller territorial units called husuu, or banners. One of the Khalkha aimak contained temple territories in addition to banners" (Vreeland, 1954:10). The focal community of Narobanchin is an example of a temple territory that has religious as well as civil administrative power. Other sub-groups of the mongol society may fall under the rule of other banners, which typically only have civil administrative powers.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, because the Narobanchin Temple territory is a unique example of a temple that has both civil and religious administrative power. (See Vreeland, 1954).

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Narobanchin territory interacts with other territories, banners, and civil administrations that all fall under the Chinese Empire. (See Vreeland, 1954).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS variable 20, Food Storage, code=2, individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: SCCS variable 232, Intensity of Cultivation, code = 2, casual agriculture, i.e., the slight or sporadic cultivation of food or other plants incidental to a primary dependence upon other subsistence practices (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: "The Narobanchin territory was required to supply transportation at two relay stations, one located inside the territory, to the north, and the other located in the neighboring banner, to the northeast. The station inside the territory was maintained by one of the Narobanchin families, as a lifetime occupation, and these people were supported here by contributions of food and clothing from the other families in the territory" (Vreeland, 1954:26).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Because Narobanchin Territory has the separate jurisdictional status of a banner, it is set up in administrative level with a banner. Subsequently, the temple performs civil duties such as taxing. "The second kind of contribution, and the more obligatory, was the kind known as alba. As mentioned earlier in discussing the political structure and [Page 112] civil administration of the territory, lay families were required to pay taxes and render certain services to the civil administration, these obligations being specified by the civil code, and being termed alba. They belonged to the same category as the civil obligations of families in a banner territory" (Vreeland, 1954:111).

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Because Narobanchin territory has individual civil jurisdiction, taxes are collected through the

temple. For other banners, "Obligations of regular taxes, transportation service, and military service were codified and a register was kept by each banner indicating the nature of each family's obligations. Families which were neither sumnai ail or hamjaanai ail were listed as sula ail (loose family) 16 and bore the regular tax and transportation obligations. Families which were sumnai ail were listed as such and bore the military as well as the tax and transportation obligations. Families which were hamjaanai ail were also listed as such although they bore the same civil obligations as the sula ail. Noble families were listed separately as taiji and bore tax obligations but with certain exemptions; they were, moreover, not obliged to supply transportation" (Vreeland, 1954:14).

Enforcement

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: SCCS variable 89, Judiciary, code=2, not local (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Warfare

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Specific families (sumnai ali) have a hereditary obligation to serve in the military if necessary. "The military establishment of the banner was of primary interest to the Chinese Empire. At the time of the original enfeoffment of each banner, the incumbent jasak had been granted the land, plus a certain quota of the families in the banner to be carried on the banner register as banner troops. These families, called sumnai ail (families of the sum) were made available to the jasak to meet any demand for troops placed on him by the emperor" (Vreeland, 1954:13).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: While the Khalka Mongols speak a unique variant of Mongolian, the languages are not associated with specific religions.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In Mongolia the official language is Mongolian. The Khalka Mongols use a variant of the official language. (eHRAF World Cultures, Culture Summary: Khalka Mongols; and Vreeland, 1973:8).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: "Mongolian time measurement is based on the lunar calendar" (Maiskii, 1921:682).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: See Vreeland, 1973:27

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: See Vreeland, 1973:27

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Mongols bought many food items from the Chinese (Vreeland, 1973:29).

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: "Like most herdsmen, the Mongols were dependent on trade for a series of commodities, some of which they could not extract from their animals or local environment, or could not make themselves, and some of which they preferred to local products and manufactures. These commodities ranged from the more essential requirements of every day living to luxury items bought primarily by persons whose position in the society demanded a certain amount of display" (Vreeland, 1973:29). The Mongols bought food and drink from the Chinese, including items such as tea, noodles, wheat flour, millet, sugar, and dried fruits.